

Derivatives of Titanium with Compounds having Bidentate Ligands. Part VI.* Derivatives with Benzoylacetone

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The reactions of titanium alkoxides and tetrachloride with benzoylacetone (benz. ac) give products similar to those obtained with acetylacetone. $TiCl_4$ (benz. ac)₂ reacts with alcohol in presence of ammonia to yield the monomeric $Ti(OR)_2$ (benz. ac)₂, which in its turn reacts with HCl to furnish the dichloride derivative. The above as well as other properties indicate the monomeric nature of $TiCl_2$ (benz. ac)₂ similar to $TiCl_2$ (ac. ac)₂.

Dilthey¹ first studied the reaction between titanium tetrachloride and benzoylacetone and the product was assigned the formula $[Ti(\text{benz. ac})_2]_2 TiCl_6$. This assumption was made on the basis of a similar compound obtained by the reaction between titanium tetrachloride and acetylacetone². Now it has been suggested that this dichloride diacetylacetone derivative of titanium is monomeric in a number of organic solvents³.

Because of the low solubility of titanium dichloride dibenzoylacetone, obtained by the reaction between titanium tetrachloride and benzoylacetone, in common organic solvents, it was not possible to determine its molecular weight.

In view of the above, the reactions between titanium alkoxides and benzoylacetone have been studied and two types of compounds: $Ti(OR)_3$ (benz. ac) and $Ti(OR)_2$ (benz.-ac)₂ have been obtained (Table I). The reactions may be represented as follows:

*Part VII published in June issue of this Journal, 1962, p. 447.

1. Dilthey, *Annalen*, 1906, **314**, 300.

2. Rosenheim *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 1823.

3. Puri and Mehrotra, *J. Less Common Metals*, 1961, **3**, 247.

Molecular weights of these compounds (Table III) have been determined in boiling benzene, which show that dialkoxide derivatives are monomeric in nature, whereas the trialkoxide derivatives show an average molecular complexity of about 1.4. This complexity can be attributed to the tendency for attaining the maximum co-ordination(8) of titanium.

Alcohol-interchange reactions have also been studied with normal and tertiary butanol, phenol, and ethylene glycol (Table II):

Titanium dialkoxide dibenzoylacetone reacts with hydrogen chloride in benzene to form titanium dichloride dibenzoylacetone:

Similarly, titanium dichloride dibenzoylacetone reacts with alcohol in presence of anhydrous ammonia and titanium dialkoxide dibenzoylacetone is obtained:

The monomeric nature of the dialkoxide compound and also the above reversible reactions suggest that titanium dichloride dibenzoylacetone may have the following plausible structure:

By the reaction between titanium tetrachloride and benzoylacetone (1:1 molar ratio) in refluxing benzene, titanium trichloride monobenzoylacetone was obtained in the form of dark red crystals. This compound reacts with ethanol exothermally with the replacement of one chlorine atom with OEt and subsequent addition of one mole of EtOH.

This is similar to the reaction between titanium tetrachloride and ethanol⁴, when titanium diethoxide dichloride with addition of a mole of ethanol is obtained.

With acetic acid also, titanium trichloride monobenzoylacetone reacts exothermally. On mild refluxing, only one atom of chlorine is replaced, but refluxing the mixture for longer time decomposes the compound, forming an equimolar mixture of titanil diacetate and basic titanium triacetate:

4. Jennings *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 637; Bradley *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1952, 2773.

These reactions are similar to the reactions of titanium tetrachloride⁵ and titanium trichloride monoacetylacetone⁶ with acetic acid.

Titanium dichloride dibenzoylacetone also reacts similarly with acetic acid, forming an equimolar mixture of titanyl diacetate and basic triacetate of titanium.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus with interchangeable standard joint was used^{3,7}. Special care was taken to exclude moisture during the experiments from the apparatus. The molecular weights were determined in a semimicro ebullimeter (Gallenkamp)³.

Titanium tetrachloride (E. Merck) and titanium alkoxide (ethoxide, isopropoxide, and butoxide⁸) were distilled before use. Benzene, acetic acid, butanol¹¹, and butanol¹ (B. D. H.) were dried as usual^{3,7}. Ethylene glycol and phenol were distilled before use. Benzoylacetone was also distilled under reduced pressure (118°/2.5 mm).

Titanium and chlorine were estimated gravimetrically. Acetic acid was estimated by titrating against a standard alkali. Ethanol and isopropanol were estimated iodimetrically⁸.

Reactions between Titanium Alkoxides and Benzoylacetone in Benzene

(i) *In 1:1 Molar Ratio.*—To titanium alkoxide in benzene was added benzoylacetone (1:1 molar ratio). The mixture on shaking became slightly hot and yellow in colour. The benzoylacetone dissolved slowly in the mixture and it was refluxed for 2 hours (bath

5. Kapoor *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1958, **35**, 157.

6. Puri and Mehrotra, unpublished.

7. Puri and Mehrotra, *J. Less Common Metals*, 1961, **3**, 253.

8. Bradley *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450.

temperature 140°). The benzene-alcohol azeotrope was then taken and the excess of benzene was removed at the column. The compound was dried under reduced pressure at 30°. An orange solid or liquid was obtained. The alcohol in the azeotrope was estimated. The titanium in the compound was also estimated (Table I, No. 1, 2, and 3).

(ii) *In 1:2 Molar Ratio.*—(a). To titanium ethoxide in benzene was added benzoylacetone in excess; the mixture became hot and yellow in colour. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours at 145° (bath temperature) and then the azeotrope was taken at 68°. On cooling, an orange-yellow solution was obtained. The solution on keeping overnight did not crystallise. The volatile component of the solution was removed under reduced pressure at 50°/0.5 mm. A light yellow solid was obtained which contained excess of benzoylacetone. This benzoylacetone was removed under reduced pressure at 121°/3 mm (at 275° bath temperature). On cooling, a dark orange solid was obtained. The ethanol in the azeotrope on estimation was found to be 2 moles of the alkoxide (Table I, No. 4).

(b). To titanium alkoxide in benzene was added benzoylacetone (1:2 molar ratio). The mixture became yellow and hot. The azeotrope was taken at the column after refluxing the mixture at 135° for about 2 hours. The excess benzene was also distilled. On cooling, a yellow-orange solution was obtained which on drying gave a yellow-orange solid or liquid. The alcohol in the azeotrope was estimated (Table I, No. 5, 6, 7).

TABLE I

Titanium alkoxide.	Benzoyl acetone.*	Product, state, and yield.	%Titanium.		Alcohol.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1. Ti(OEt) ₄ (4.41g.)	3.20 g.	Ti(OEt) ₃ (benz. ac); light orange crystals (6.33g.); m. p. 82°	13.94	13.95	0.80 g.	0.86g.
2. Ti(OPri) ₄ (2.87g.)	1.65	Ti(OPri) ₃ (benz. ac); light orange solid (3.9g.); m. p. 88°	12.36	12.44	0.60	0.60
3. Ti(OBu ⁿ) ₄ (1.92g.)	0.92	Ti(OBu ⁿ) ₃ (benz. ac); orange viscous liquid (2.34g.)	11.34	11.18	..	..
4. Ti(OEt) ₄ (3.17g.)	7.50	Ti(OEt) ₂ (benz. ac) ₂ ; dark orange solid (after removing the excess benzoylacetone)	11.01	10.43	1.19	1.27
5. Ti(OEt) ₄ (14.17g.)	20.5	Ti(OEt) ₂ (benz. ac) ₂ ; light yellow solid (27.77g.); m. p. 119°	10.42	10.43	5.09	5.70
6. Ti(OPri) ₄ (3.71g.)	4.32	Ti(OPri) ₂ (benz. ac) ₂ ; orange yellow solid (6.38g.); m. p. 89°	9.64	9.83	1.55	1.56
7. Ti(OBu ⁿ) ₄ (2.92g.)	2.80	Ti(OBu ⁿ) ₂ (benz. ac) ₂ ; orange yellow viscous liquid (4.49g.)	9.30	9.27	..	..

*Benzoylacetone (benz. ac)

Reactions between Titanium Trialkoxide Monobenzoylacetone and Higher Alcohols in Benzene

To titanium trialkoxide monobenzoylacetone in benzene was added higher alcohol. No heat was evolved and no colour change was observed except in the case of phenol where the solution became dark orange. The mixture was refluxed for 1 hour (120° bath temperature) and then the azeotrope was taken. The mixture was cooled and dried under reduced pressure. The compound obtained was either orange, viscous liquid or foamy solid. The alcohol in the azeotrope was estimated (Table II, No 1—4.).

Reactions between Titanium Dialkoxide Dibenzoylacetone and Higher Alcohols in Benzene

Titanium dialkoxide dibenzoylacetone was dissolved in benzene and to it was added higher alcohol. Except in the case of phenol, no change in colour was observed. The heat was also not evolved. The reaction mixture was refluxed and the azeotrope was taken. After cooling and drying under reduced pressure at 40°, orange viscous liquid or foamy solid was obtained (Table II, No. 5—8).

TABLE II

No.	Reactants.	Product, state, and yield.	%Titanium.		Alcohol.		
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	
1.	Ti(OEt) ₃ (benz.ac) BuOH ⁿ	(1.44 g.) (2.30g.)	Ti(OBu ⁿ) ₃ (benz.ac); orange viscous liquid (1.09g.)	11.11	11.18	0.58 g.	0.577g.
2.	Ti(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (benz.ac) BuOH ^t	(1.33g.) (2.00g.)	Ti(OBu ^t) ₃ (benz.ac); orange viscous liquid (1.41g.)	11.37	11.18	..	..
3.	Ti(OEt) ₃ (benz.ac) Phenol	(0.42g.) (0.33g.)	Ti(OPh) ₃ (benz.ac); highly viscous dark orange liquid (0.57g.)	9.92	9.8	0.16	0.17
4.	Ti(OEt) ₃ (benz.ac) Ethylene glycol	(0.84g.) (0.15g.)	Ti(O ₂ C ₂ H ₄)(OEt)(benz.ac); orange foamy solid (0.76g.); m.p. 120°	15.75	15.24	0.21	0.22
5.	Ti(OEt) ₂ (benz.ac) ₂ BuOH ⁿ	(1.63g.) (0.70g.)	Ti(OBu ⁿ) ₂ (benz.ac) ₂ ; orange viscous liquid (1.81g.)	9.34	9.30	0.32	0.32
6.	Ti(OPr ⁱ) ₂ (benz.ac) ₂ BuOH ^t	(1.79g.) (2.00g.)	Ti(OBu ^t) ₂ (benz.ac) ₂ ; orange-red viscous liquid (2.01g.)	9.36	9.30	0.44	0.44
7.	Ti(OEt) ₂ (benz.ac) ₂ Phenol	(3.35g.) (1.37g.)	Ti(OPh) ₂ (benz.ac) ₂ ; highly viscous, dark orange liquid (4.01g.)	9.80	8.60	0.63	0.66
8.	Ti(OEt) ₂ (benz.ac) ₂ Ethylene glycol	(6.67g.) (0.92g.)	Ti(O ₂ C ₂ H ₄)(benz.ac) ₂ ; orange foamy solid (6.1g.)	11.04	11.14	1.28	1.33

Reaction between Titanium Tetrachloride and Benzoylacetone in the Ratio of 1:1 in Benzene

To titanium tetrachloride (5.64 g.) in benzene (60 ml) was added benzoylacetone (4.8 g.). The solution became red and hot. Hydrogen chloride gas was evolved as dense fumes. The mixture was refluxed at a bath temperature of 140° for 6 hours till all the hydrogen chloride was removed. The mixture was cooled and kept overnight. Dark red shining crystals were obtained (8.7 g.) which were dried under reduced pressure at 30° after decanting the supernatant liquid. [Found: Ti, 15.10; Cl, 33.90. Calc. for Ti (benz. ac)-Cl₂: Ti, 15.2; Cl, 33.75%].

Reaction between Titanium Trichloride Monobenzoylacetone and Excess Ethanol

To titanium trichloride monobenzoylacetone (1.51 g.) was added ethanol (15 ml). The mixture became slightly hot on dissolving the compound. On refluxing, hydrogen chloride gas was evolved. After 3 hours, when all the hydrogen chloride was removed, the mixture was cooled. A dark red solution was obtained. The excess of ethanol was removed by distillation and the compound was dried under reduced pressure at 70° (bath temperature). A highly viscous red liquid was obtained (1.79 g.). [Found: Ti, 13.04; Cl, 18.70. TiCl₂ (OEt) (benz. ac). EtOH requires Ti, 12.92; Cl, 19.1%].

Reaction between Titanium Trichloride Monobenzoylacetone and Acetic Acid in Excess on Mild Refluxing

To titanium trichloride monobenzoylacetone (0.6 g.) was added acetic acid (~10ml). The mixture became slightly hot and changed its colour from dark red to dark orange. It was refluxed at 120° for 2 hours when all the hydrogen chloride gas was removed. On cooling and keeping overnight, dark orange crystals (0.43 g.) were obtained. The crystals were dried under reduced pressure after decanting the supernatant liquid and washing with acetic acid. [Found: Ti, 13.98; Cl, 20.43. TiCl₂(OAc) (benz. ac) requires Ti, 14.1; Cl, 20.9%].

Reaction between Titanium Trichloride Monobenzoylacetone and Acetic Acid on Continued Refluxing

To titanium trichloride monobenzoylacetone (1.37 g.) was added acetic acid (15ml). Slowly the compound dissolved and heat was produced. The reaction mixture turned orange from red. It was refluxed at 180° for 2 hours when hydrogen chloride was evolved. The compound then slowly decomposed and more hydrogen, chloride gas was evolved. The refluxing was continued till all the hydrogen chloride was removed (8 hours). A yellowish white solid (0.6 g.) separated from the acid. This was dried under reduced pressure at 30° after decanting the supernatant liquid and washing with acetic acid. { Found: Ti, 22.09; OAc, 70.33. Calc. for an equimolar mixture of TiO(OAc)₂ and O[Ti(OAc)₃]₂: Ti, 22.2; OAc, 72.8% }.

Reaction between Titanium Tetrachloride and Benzoylacetone in Excess in Benzene

To titanium tetrachloride (3.5 g.) in benzene (70 ml) was added benzoylacetone (9.4 g.). The mixture became red and hot. Dense fumes of hydrogen chloride

were evolved. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 hours to remove all the HCl gas. On cooling dark red crystals settled down. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the red crystals (5.7 g.) after washing with benzene were dried under reduced pressure at 40°. [Found: Ti, 10.7; Cl, 16.17. Calc. for $TiCl_2(\text{benz. ac})_2$: Ti, 10.88; Cl, 16.10%].

Reaction between Titanium Dichloride Dibenzoylacetone and Acetic Acid in Excess

Acetic acid (10 ml) was added to titanium dichloride dibenzoylacetone (1.04 g.). The compound did not dissolve immediately, but on refluxing at 180° it dissolved slowly. After about 2 hours' refluxing the compound decomposed slowly and HCl gas was liberated. A yellowish white solid separated from the acid. The refluxing was continued till all the HCl gas had evolved (8 hours). After cooling, the compound (0.51 g.) was filtered, washed with acetic acid, and dried under reduced pressure at 30°. { Found: Ti, 22.05; OAc, 70.33. Calc. for an equimolar mixture of $TiO(\text{OAc})_2$ and $O[Ti(\text{OAc})_2]_2$: Ti, 22.2; OAc, 72.8%}.

TABLE III

Compound.	Molecular weights.		
	Obs.	Average.	Calc.
1. $Ti(\text{OEt})_2(\text{benz. ac})$	466.5, 466.2, 472.1	466.2	344.0
2. $Ti(\text{OPri})_2(\text{benz. ac})$	463.1, 477.9, 498.3	470.4	366.0
3. $Ti(\text{OEt})_2(\text{benz. ac})_2$	521.7, 514.6, 514.2, 521.1	517.9	480.0
4. $Ti(\text{OPri})_2(\text{benz. ac})_2$	494.4, 488.8, 492.0	491.7	488.0
5. $Ti(\text{OBun})_2(\text{benz. ac})_2$	622.4, 600.5, 638.7	623.5	516.0
6. $Ti(\text{OBu}^t)_2(\text{benz. ac})_2$	561.1, 573.2, 563.8	566.0	516.0

Reaction between Titanium Dichloride Dibenzoylacetone and Ethanol in presence of Ammonia in Benzene

To titanium dichloride dibenzoylacetone (2.08 g.) was added ethanol (15 ml). On shaking the alcohol became slightly red. To this was added benzene (40 ml). No heat was produced, but the colour of the solution changed very slightly from dark red to orange. Dry ammonia was passed through the mixture with constant shaking. After about half hour, the mixture became hot and a white precipitate of ammonium chloride was formed. After four hours' interval the mixture was cooled. It was then filtered and the yellow filtrate was refluxed to remove the excess of ammonia. The excess of solvent was also removed by distillation. The remaining solvent was removed under reduced pressure when a light yellow solid was obtained (1.80 g.). [Found: Ti, 10.24. Calc. for $Ti(\text{OEt})_2(\text{benz. ac})_2$: Ti, 10.4%].

Reaction between Titanium Dioxide Dibenzoylacetone and HCl

To a solution of titanium dioxide dibenzoylacetone (1.91 g.) in benzene (40 ml) was passed dry HCl gas. After about 15 minutes, the colour of the solution changed from yellow-orange to dark red. Very little heat was produced. The gas was passed for 3 hours when the mixture became cold. It was kept overnight and dark red crystals were deposited (1.45 g.). The crystals were dried under reduced pressure at 40° after decanting the supernatant liquid. [Found: Ti, 10.34; Cl, 16.29. Calc. for $TiCl_2(benz.ac)_2$: Ti, 10.88; Cl, 16.1%].

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